

Enhancing Network Performance and Reducing Power Consumption in Elastic Optical Networks with Deep Reinforcement Learning

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Abstract—Achieving a sustainable network, striking a balance between transport capacity and power consumption reduction, is nowadays a critical challenge of paramount importance. In Elastic Optical Networks (EONs), a common approach involves designing effective energy-aware Routing Spectrum Assignment (EA-RSA) algorithms to provision optical connections while conserving network power. In this context, we introduce a novel EA-RSA solution which exploits the advantages of Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) to optimize the trade-off between network throughput and power consumption. Through dynamic generation of optical connections with diverse bandwidth and latency requirements, the trained DRL EA-RSA agent is comprehensively compared to two baseline heuristics: k-shortest path routing with first-fit spectrum assignment strategy (KSP-FF), prioritizing connection provisioning, and a modified energy-aware KSP-FF primarily focused on minimizing power consumption. The results indicate that the trained DRL agent excels in adapting to network conditions, achieving an enhanced trade-off between network performance and power consumption.

Index Terms—Elastic Optical Networks, Deep Reinforcement Learning, Network Power Consumption

I. INTRODUCTION

Today, the ICT industry consumes 5%-9% of total electricity [1]. To enhance sustainability from economic and energy perspectives, it prioritizes greener devices, adaptive power management aligned with traffic demands, and advanced energy-aware routing and resource selection algorithms. Herein, we focus on the latter strategy within elastic optical transport networks (EON). The primary objective is to dynamically provision optical connection services that meet specific requirements, such as bandwidth and latency, while concurrently reducing network power consumption [2]. Typically, this is achieved through the implementation of energy-aware routing and spectrum assignment (EA-RSA)

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algorithms [3]. Such algorithms, often based on heuristics, aim to minimize the activation (i.e., *powered up*) of the Optical Line System (OLS) devices such as reconfigurable optical add-drop multiplexers (ROADMs) and optical line amplifiers (OLAs), to conserve the network power. However, minimizing network element activation has drawbacks, including degraded network performance and reduced optical spectrum utilization, resulting in increased connectivity service blocking. In practice, optical connections tend to be set up through routes traversing larger number of active/powered up nodes and links. Thereby, meeting constraints adhered to EON like spectrum continuity and contiguity becomes more challenging. Hence, addressing the energy-aware routing problem is crucial to optimize the trade-off between power consumption and network performance, specifically in ensuring the successful provisioning of optical services.

In the realm of autonomous control functions handling the lifecycle management of optical connectivity services (e.g., provisioning, restoration, etc.), there is a growing focus on leveraging Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning (AI/ML) techniques. Notably, Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) has emerged as a promising AI/ML strategy. Recent efforts have been directed towards exploiting DRL in RSA algorithms to develop trained agents that globally optimize routing decisions targeting diverse service requirements [4], [5]. Such enhancements are achieved from various viewpoints: efficient spectral resources utilization [5], [6], improved selection of operational modes (i.e., modulation formats) at the transceivers [7], more effectively meeting connectivity requirements such as end-to-end latency [8]), or applying proactive spectrum defragmentation [9]. To our knowledge, the use of DRL techniques to enhance the trade-off between network throughput and overall power consumption in EON has not been explored. Therefore, we introduce an innovative DRL-assisted EA-RSA strategy (EA-DRL). This solution excels in adapting to network conditions to optimize the mentioned trade-off between throughput and power consumption.

The EA-DRL approach is compared against two heuristic solutions: i) *K-Shortest Path First Fit* (KSP-FF), prioritizing routing services over power consumption reduction, and ii)

EA-KSP-FF, primarily focusing on minimizing network power consumption. Optical connections dynamically arrive and depart, demanding varying bandwidth (i.e., spectral resources) and latency requirements. The evaluation utilizes three metrics: the average blocked bandwidth ratio (BBR), the average network power consumption (in kW), and the average served network throughput (in Gb/s). Detailed discussions follow regarding the performance of the three RSAs concerning diverse bandwidth and latency requirements. In summary, this study demonstrates that leveraging DRL techniques significantly improves the balance between network performance and reduced power consumption.

II. POWER CONSUMPTION MODEL IN EON

Figure 1 illustrates an example of the aggregate network power consumption incurred when establishing a new optical connection across the OLS, i.e., traversing powered-up ROADMs and OLAs. The power consumption of an active ROADMs (P_{ROADM}) depends on: *i*) the so-called environment power (i.e., P_{idle}) including the energy for the fans, the control system, the optical backplane, etc.; and *ii*) the consumed power of the active optical line boards/ports (OLPs) which do interconnect adjacent ROADMs, i.e., P_{OLP} . OLPs are formed by various elements such as Wavelength Selected Switches (WSSs), Optical Amplifiers and mux/demux. Hence, the total power consumption for an active optical switch is given by $P_{ROADM} = P_{idle} + P_{OLP}$, considering only the active OLPs.

Fig. 1. Power consumption of an end-to-end connection within EON OLS

On the other hand, activated optical fibers (links) equipped with a pool of OLAs also contribute to the overall network power consumption. The power consumption of such links (P_{link}) can be determined by the sum of individual OLAs' power consumption, represented as $P_{link} = \sum P_{OLA}$. Note that when a network device (i.e., ROADMs, ports, and optical link), is powered up to support an optical connection adding another flow through the same device does not result in increased power consumption. Hence, a device has two states: *active*, when it consumes power while transporting one or more optical connection; and *slept down*, where no connection utilizes the device, resulting in no power consumption. In the example, a new optical flow is set up between ROADMs S1 and S14. The figure shows the total power consumption in the path S1-S13-S14. The values used to calculate the optical connection power consumption are detailed in Tab. I.

TABLE I
EON OLS POWER CONSUMPTION VALUES

Notation	Description	Value
P_{OLA}	Power Consumption on an activated OLA	12.0 W
P_{ROADM}	Power Consumption of an active ROADM	$P_{idle} + \sum P_{OLP}$
P_{idle}	ROADM <i>environment</i> power consumption (i.e., control, fans, etc.) regardless of connection services	150.0 W
P_{OLP}	ROADM Optical Line Port /Board Power Consumption	85.0 W

III. ENERGY-AWARE RSA PROBLEM

An optical connection demand D is represented by the tuple (s, d, b, l) , where s and d denote the source and destination nodes of D , b represents the requested bandwidth (in Gb/s), and l represents the maximum end-to-end latency (in ms). The latter is computed as the cumulative delay across the traversed links forming the path. As dynamic demands D s arrive, RSA algorithms are executed to find a feasible spatial path and spectral resources (Frequency Slots, FSs) that meet D requirements (i.e., b and l) while adhering to EON constraints such as spectrum continuity and contiguity. In this context, a widely recognized RSA approach is the K-Shortest Path (KSP) solution with First-Fit spectrum assignment, KSP-FF. This algorithm seeks up to K paths that meet the EON constraints while minimizing the number of hops. If two or more paths have the same number of hops, preference is given to paths with lower aggregated latency between s and d nodes. Thus, the K paths are sorted by the number of hops and resulting end-to-end latency. For each path, it is indicated the set of available FSs fulfilling the b demand that satisfy the spectral constraints. The selected FS to accommodate D is determined by the the First-Fit approach. This solution is widely used as a benchmark due to its balanced consideration of computational complexity (scalability) and performance (i.e., connection blocking).

To deal with the energy-efficient problem, the EA-KSP-FF approach extends KSP-FF to obtain K paths which aims to minimize network power consumption. That is, for each k^{th} path, it is calculated the increase in network power consumption if the optical connection is provisioned (refer to the above energy model). The K paths are sorted in ascending order based on their number of hops, power consumption increase, and accumulated delay. Thus, EA-KSP-FF favors routing D through already powered-up/active devices to save power, rather than activating slept down network elements. By doing so, it is likely that D demands are routed over longer paths (in terms of hops and links) to favor re-utilizing active ROADMs and links' OLAs. Consequently, spectral resources experience heightened usage, which might negatively impact in both throughput and connection blocking.

A. Proposed DRL-based Energy Aware Routing Solution

To achieve a more optimal equilibrium between network performance and power consumption, we advocate leveraging

an offline-trained DRL agent, denoted as *EA-DRL*. The goal of EA-DRL is to formulate an optimized policy/model that improves network energy efficiency that is, increasing the overall throughput without causing a substantial rise in power consumption. During training the agent, a Deep Neural Network (DNN) learns to make good decisions interacting with the *environment* comprising the EON state representation (i.e., ROADMs connectivity and spectrum utilization in each fiber link) and the D requests. This is accomplished through both exploration and exploitation processes, enabling the update of the agent’s knowledge (policy) at a given instance t (i.e., *step*). This update involves mapping the current network state (denoted by s_t) with the adopted action (i.e., a_t), the subsequent state (s_{t+1}), and the received environmental feedback (i.e., rewards, r_t). The DRL system is mathematically modelled as a Markov Decision Process (MDP) [5], [8], [9] typically described by a tuple formed by *observation/state* space, *action* space, and *reward* function described below:

The *Observation/State* Space (s_t) consists of a collection of defined attributes characterizing the k^{th} candidate path that fulfills D requirements at a given step/state t . The calculation of the K paths is carried out by implementing the EA-KSP-FF algorithm. The considered attributes, as illustrated in Fig. 2, include:

- Two *one-hot* arrays describing both D s and d nodes.
- Detailed features of the end-to-end available spectrum for each k^{th} path. These include an array of three elements specifying: i) the number of nominal central frequencies (NCFs) constituting the first available FS block [5], ii) the NCF position/index (i^{th}) of the first available FS block, and iii) the average size (in NCFs) of all the available FS blocks.
- The existing power consumption (in W), attributed to current connections and consumed by the ROADMs and OLAs along the k^{th} path.
- Requested number of NCFs fulfilling the demanded D bandwidth (i.e., b).
- Resulting end-to-end delay through all the links forming the k^{th} path.
- The D requested latency, i.e. l .

Fig. 2. Observation space representation

The *Action* Space (a_t) describes the set of discrete actions the agent can adopt within an environment. Herein, each action is associated to a specific k^{th} path computed for D at step s_t .

The *Reward* function (r_t) assigns a numerical score to the chosen action within a specific state. For eligible actions, i.e., feasible k^{th} paths for D , the reward function is expressed in Eq. 1. It takes into account two crucial values: the requested D bandwidth (b) and the increase/*cost* of network power through the selected k^{th} path, referred to as $CostPathPower_{k^{th}}$. The reward function is computed as the sum of both values. The b component encourages the selection of actions that guide the agent to provision as many bandwidth as possible, enhancing overall network throughput. The second r_t component is the inverse of the $CostPathPower_{k^{th}}$. This encourages the agent to choose paths/actions that minimize the increase in power consumption when deploying D s. Specifically, the $CostPathPower_{k^{th}}$ reflects the rise in power consumption if sleep down elements (i.e., ROADMs, optical line ports, or link’s OLAs) need to be powered up. Hence, the DRL agent is trained to make optimal decisions to increase the accommodation of connections while attempting to conserve the power consumption. If no feasible actions/paths exist, due to either lack of available FSs or unable to meet latency needs, the reward is set to a negative value of -10 .

$$r_t = \begin{cases} b + \frac{1}{CostPathPower_{k^{th}}}, & \text{if } D \text{ is set up} \\ -10, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In this section, we present the performance evaluation for the proposed EA-DRL approach, comparing it to two benchmark RSA heuristics, KSP-FF and EA-KSP-FF. Different dynamic traffic intensities, involving variations in the arrival and departure times of D requests, are considered. The comparison is carried out in terms of the average BBR (the ratio between the blocked bandwidth in b/s and the overall requested bandwidth), average network power consumption (in kW), and average network throughput (in Gb/s). Additionally, discussions are provided regarding how the three RSAs behave concerning different D bandwidth and latency requirements.

A. Network Topology and Connection Service Generation

The network topology is a transport EON comprising 14 ROADMs and 21 bidirectional links as depicted in Fig. 3. Each optical link supports 128 NCFs in C-band spaced 6.25 GHz. Link attributes in terms of fiber distance (in km) and delay (in ms) are labelled on each edge as $[delay, distance]$. The link distance is used to account for the number of OLAs where an OLA is placed every 80 km. On the other hand, the delay link features is used to compute paths fulfilling D latency requirements. Specific power consumption values/figures (see Section II) of ROADMs, optical ports, and OLAs are shown in Tab. I.

For each D , the source and destination nodes are randomly selected from a subset of 9 nodes, namely [S1, S2, S3, S9,

Fig. 3. EON Network Topology - Edge labels [delay, distance]

S10, S12, S13, S14], out of the 14 ROADMs constituting the EON. Thereby, these nodes can act as ingress, egress, or transit nodes, while the remaining nodes exclusively operate as transit nodes. This design provides flexibility to the EA-RSA approaches, allowing it to decide whether transit-only nodes are either activated to accommodate D requests or remaining in slept-down status to conserve power consumption. Note that if all 14 ROADMs operate as source/destination nodes, there might be instances, especially for high traffic intensities, where no discernible power consumption differences are observed among the RSA approaches. The selected subset of source-destination nodes is deemed sufficient to generalize the following results. The K value to compute the candidates paths for all the RSA algorithms is set to 5.

The D requests are generated using a Poisson process with an inter-arrival time set to 50 s. The D duration is exponentially modeled, with the mean Holding Time (HT) varied between 2000 and 5000 s to generate a range of traffic intensities. The requested D data rate (i.e., b) is randomly chosen from the set [200, 400, 800] Gb/s. We assume a single modulation scheme DP-QPSK operating at 25 Gbaud/s (i.e., 100 Gb/s) which requires a FS of 12.5 GHz, that is 2 NCFs with 6.25 GHz channel spacing. Consequently, requested D data rates are mapped into FSs formed by [4, 8, 16] NCFs. Combining diverse modulation formats will be addressed in future works. The objective of the present work is to perform a comprehensive evaluation of the proposed EA-DRL and heuristics in terms of network performance (specifically, BBR and served throughput), along with an assessment of overall power consumption. Finally, the D latency requirements are randomly selected from the set [7, 8, 9] ms.

The EA-DRL training model utilizes a policy optimizer

named *maskable* Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO), which is a variation of the actor-critic architecture. It comprises 3 hidden fully connected layers with 128 neurons for the actor neural network (NN) and 5 hidden layers with 128 neurons for the critic NN. For a EON formed by N nodes, the size of the vector for the actor and critic NNs is $2 \times |N| + k \times 7$ (refer to Fig. 2). The output layer is a vector with K elements representing the probability of choosing one of the candidate paths. The learning rate is set to 10^{-5} with a discount factor of 0.95. The training involves 10^7 optical connections, comprising 1000 episodes with a length of 10^4 requests. The training traffic load was set to $HT = 4000$ s, resulting in a traffic intensity that allowed the training to achieve a targeted BBR around 10^{-1} . Figure 4 displays the BBR for the EA-KSP-FF heuristic and different training episodes for the EA-DRL model. As mentioned earlier, one of the objectives of the EA-DRL strategy is to increase the throughput, which is reflected in reducing the BBR. From the figure, it is evident that as the number of episodes grows, the BBR performance of EA-DRL outperforms the EA-KSP-FF heuristic. This improvement is attributed to the EA-DRL agent which gradually learns optimized RSA decisions for various network conditions, as shown for episodes beyond 200.

Fig. 4. Training phase of the EA-DRL mechanism

B. Bandwidth Blocked Ratio and Network Power Consumption

Irrespective of the underlying transport technology, the challenge of energy-efficient routing strategies necessitates a comprehensive performance analysis from two critical perspectives: network performance measured by BBR or average throughput, and network power consumption. A trade-off exists between these aspects, as improving one might lead to deteriorate the other. Bearing this in mind, Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 illustrate the BBR and average network power consumption across diverse HTs for KSP-FF, EA-KSP-FF and the trained model EA-DRL. Each data point is derived from the generation of 10^5 D requests under the previously mentioned traffic generation assumptions.

The KSP-FF approach consistently achieves the best (i.e., lowest) BBR for all the traffic loads, albeit at the expense of exhibiting the worst performance (i.e., highest) in terms of network power consumption. The reason is that KSP-FF prioritizes optimizing spectrum resource utilization to accommodate more flows, disregarding power consumption. By adopting the EA-KSP-FF strategy, a notable reduction in power consumption is achieved, particularly under low/moderate traffic loads. Compared to KSP-FF, the EA-KSP-FF approach accomplishes up to 27.8% of power reduction for HT=2000s. Recall that EA-KSP-FF is designed to establish D requests through active ROADMs and links (i.e., OLAs) to conserve network power. However, this leads to longer paths in order to utilize active devices, increasing spectral usage and complicating both spectral constraint fulfillment and meeting maximum latency requirement. To enhance this, the trained EA-DRL model is devised to significantly improve the BBR compared to EA-KSP-FF, particularly evident for low to moderate traffic loads. This improvement ranges from 35% at HT=2000 to 3% at HT=5000. Certainly, the EA-DRL agent is trained to learn optimal RSA decisions, resulting in outperforming the network performance (BBR) of the EA-KSP-FF heuristic. However, this improvement comes at the cost of consuming more network power compared to that heuristic (up to 35% at HT=2000 and 1.4% at HT=5000). Note that as the traffic intensity increases, the distinctions between the three approaches in terms of both BBR and network power consumption tend to diminish. This is because optical resources become more occupied, making it more challenging to meet spectral constraints and latency demands. In such circumstances, the KSP-FF heuristic emerges as the preferred solution.

Fig. 5. Performance on Blocking Bandwidth Ratio (BBR) vs HT (s)

Finally, another noteworthy metric to be outlined pertains to the performance achieved by the three RSA strategies concerning the average network throughput (in Tb/s), as presented in Table II. As expected, KSP-FF heuristic does attain the highest average network throughput for all the traffic loads. Focusing on the energy-aware RSA algorithms, EA-KSP-FF and EA-DRL, the learned policies of the trained model lead to an enhanced overall throughput. The rationale

Fig. 6. Performance on Av. Network Power Consumption (kW) vs HT (s)

TABLE II
AVERAGE NETWORK THROUGHPUT (Tb/s)

HT(s)	KSP-FF	EA-KSP-FF	EA-DRL
2000	18.96	18.37	18.91
3500	32.62	31.71	31.90
5000	44.01	43.17	43.25

behind this is associated with both a more efficient utilization of the optical spectrum and an enhanced ability to meet the D latency requirement when the trained EA-DRL agent is adopted instead of the EA-KSP-FF algorithm.

In essence, EA-DRL optimizes RSA decisions for different network states, striking a balance between network performance and power consumption when dynamically provisioning D requests.

C. Performance on the Optical Connections' Requirements

In this section, we analyze the performance of the RSA approaches for each individual D requirement, i.e., requested data rates (b) and latency values (l). The goal is to evaluate how each approach behaves when serving D requests with more stringent requirements, specifically highest b and lowest l . To achieve this, for different HTs, it is determined the percentage of successful connection establishments over requested ones for each b (i.e., [200, 400, 800] Gb/s) and l (i.e., [7, 8, 9] ms).

As indicated in Table III, KSP-FF achieves the highest successful establishment of D s for all the requested data rates. Recall that this accomplishment comes at the expense of incurring the highest network power consumption. As traffic load increases, optical resources are more utilized which complicates the establishment of upcoming D requests. This is particularly noticeable for D requesting higher b , which involve FSs necessitating larger number of NCFs. Thereby, RSA algorithms encounter more challenges in meeting spectrum constraints. Focusing on the energy-aware RSA approaches, note that for all HT values, the trained EA-DRL agent leads to

TABLE III
CONNECTION ESTABLISHMENTS (%) ACROSS BIT RATE REQUIREMENT
(b)

HT(s)	b (Gb/s)	KSP-FF	EA-KSP-FF	EA-DRL
2000	200	100%	97.50%	98.5%
	400	99.97%	97.47%	98.39%
	800	99.96%	96.23%	97.53%
3500	200	99.99%	98.94%	99.27%
	400	99.89%	98.58%	98.93%
	800	97.97%	94.31%	94.79%
5000	200	99.96%	99.55%	99.76%
	400	99.00%	98.12%	98.36%
	800	89.34%	86.83%	86.91%

TABLE IV
CONNECTION ESTABLISHMENTS (%) ACROSS LATENCY REQUIREMENT
(l)

HT(s)	l (ms)	KSP-FF	EA-KSP-FF	EA-DRL
2000	7	99.96%	92.72%	95.55%
	8	99.99%	99.02%	99.12%
	9	100%	99.43%	99.71%
3500	7	98.91%	94.78%	95.70%
	8	99.41%	98.23%	98.41%
	9	99.51%	98.80%	98.86%
5000	7	95.22%	93.08%	93.61%
	8	96.38%	95.32%	95.36%
	9	96.67%	95.94%	96.06%

achieve a more 'fair' distribution of connection establishments across all b requests when compared to EA-KSP-FF. In other words, the trained model EA-DRL enables a more effective fulfillment of demands with more stringent bandwidth bandwidth requirements.

The Table IV illustrates the connection establishment percentages for the RSA algorithms for diverse latency requirements. As the latency requirement becomes more stringent (i.e., lowest), the algorithms have more difficulties to meet them. Once again, the KSP-FF strategy achieves the best results. However, noteworthy is the observation that the trained model succeeds in establishing more connections than the EA-KSP-FF solution for all requested latency values. This difference is particularly pronounced for the most restrictive requirements, i.e., $l = 7$ ms. Therefore, we can assert that the EA-DRL agent's model adapts more effectively to different network states compared to the heuristic solution EA-KSP-FF. This allows it to generally meet more demanding D requirements: higher bandwidths and lower latencies.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a novel energy-aware RSA algorithm leveraging the advantages of a trained DRL agent when dynamically provisioning optical services with diverse bandwidth and latency requirements. The aim of this approach (referred to as EA-DRL) is to attain a better trade-off between average network throughput and network power consumption. Details of the proposed EA-DRL model are presented, and it is compared to two RSA heuristics: KSP-FF, prioritizing

connection establishment over power consumption reduction, and EA-KSP-FF, which aims at mainly reducing the overall network power consumption. The comparison is conducted across diverse traffic intensities in terms of BBR, average network power consumption, and throughput. Additionally, the performance of the three RSA algorithms concerning diverse connection requirements, such as bandwidth and latency, is also discussed. From the obtained results, we can assert that the EA-DRL model can better adapt its policies to different network conditions, resulting in an enhanced trade-off between network performance and power consumption compared to both heuristic approaches. For the two energy-aware RSA solutions, it is also worth noting that the trained EA-DRL model achieves a higher and more balanced percentage of connection establishment with diverse requirements in both data rate and latency.

This study highlights the advantages offered by trained DRL agents when applied to complex problems, such as the dynamic execution of energy-aware RSA algorithms in EON with stringent bandwidth and latency needs. Future work will focus on extending the evaluation to consider other power-consuming network devices, such as bandwidth-variable transceivers, and explore other transport infrastructures, e.g., multi-band optical networks.

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